

GRAMMATICAL PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH AND THE METHOD USED TO ELIMINATE THEM.

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ABSTRACT: This article is dedicated to students who have difficulty learning English grammar and make many grammar mistakes while learning the language.

KEY WORDS: Tense, active voice, passive voice, conjunction, verbs, nouns, adjectives, words, adverbs, subjects and objects. Translation as a term is generally connected with the activity or interaction of delivering the content of a source language word, word-gathering, or sentence in the objective language or with the consequence of the cycle of delivering.

Introduction

The grammatical design of the language is a significant piece of its general framework, no less significant, truth be told, than its dictionary. The components of the grammatical design, for example, attach types of emphasis and inference, syntactic examples, word request, and so forth, serve to convey implications which are generally alluded to as "grammatical" or "primary" implications, as unmistakable from lexical implications. The delivery of these implications during the process of translation is a significant problem identifying with the overall problem of translation comparability which should be considered final. Grammatical types of different languages without a doubt, very only occasionally correspond completely regarding the extent of their importance and capacity. As a rule, there is just incomplete comparability that is the grammatical implications communicated by grammatical structures, however apparently indistinguishable, of two different languages agree just in a piece of their importance and differ in different pieces of similar meanings.

1. Grammatical problems

Grammatical problems can incorporate inquiries of transience, viewpoint – where the action word demonstrates if the activity is proceeding or finished, pronouns, and regardless of whether to make the subject pronoun express.

2. Translating Language Structure

Each language sits inside a characterized structure with its own settled upon rules. The intricacy and peculiarity of this system straightforwardly associate with the difficulty of translation. A basic sentence in English has a subject, verb, and object — in that request. For instance, “she eats pizza.” But few out of every odd language shares this structure. Farsi commonly follows an arrangement of the subject, then, at that point object, then, at that point verb. Furthermore, in Arabic, subject pronouns really become part of the actual verb. Subsequently, translators every now and again need to add, eliminate, and modify source words to successfully impart in the objective language.

3. Grammatical problems of translation

Following are the grammatical problems of translation:

- Analytical and synthetic character of language
- Auxiliary verbs usage
- Structural errors
- Strict word order

It is possible to resolve these load of problems simply because of expert translation, utilizing grammatical transformations. Modifications in the underlying type of language units performed fully intent on accomplishing loyalty in the translation are alluded to as translator’s transformations. They are completed either as a result of the incongruence of the objective language method for expression, which makes the transplantation of some source language units inconceivable, or to hold the style of the source language entries and in this way keep up with the expressiveness of the source language sense units.

Syntax (SYN):

A syntax error occurs when the arrangement of words or other elements of a sentence does not conform to the syntactic rules of the target language. Errors in this category include improper modification, lack of parallelism, unnatural word order, and run-on structure. If incorrect syntax changes or obscures the meaning, the error is more serious and may be classified as a different type of error using the Flowchart and Framework .

5. Cohesion (COH):

The term “cohesion” refers to the way meanings and ideas link to each other in a logical chain or sequence within or across sentences or through a longer text. It is an overarching term that covers a dozen different devices by which this logical linking is achieved and maintained, usually grouped under four main types of

grammatical cohesion: reference, substitution, ellipsis, and conjunction, and a fifth category, named lexical cohesion. A cohesion error occurs when a text is hard to follow because of the inappropriate or incorrect use of any of these devices. For the purposes of the present document, cohesion is best explained by reference to a brief series of examples that illustrate each of the five types and their sub-types. **Faithfulness (F):** A faithfulness error occurs when the target text does not respect the meaning of the source text as much as possible. Candidates are asked to translate the meaning and intent of the source text, not to rewrite it or improve upon it. The grader will carefully compare the translation to the source text. If a “creative” rendition changes the meaning, an error will be marked. If recasting a sentence or paragraph—i.e., altering the order of its major elements—destroys the flow, changes the emphasis, or obscures the author’s intent, an error may be marked. Comprehension questions

This technique is generally used in teaching any foreign language. In this, an unseen passage will be given to the students out of which they will be asked some questions and they are expected to answer those questions in their native language or the foreign language whatever they want. The main purpose of this technique is to find out that whether the students are able to translate the passage in their language and able to find out the answers. Grammar errors can undermine your credibility, clarity, and professionalism as a writer. Whether you are writing an email, a blog post, a report, or a novel, you want to avoid making mistakes that distract your readers or confuse your message. Fortunately, there are some effective ways to address grammar errors in your writing and improve your skills. Here are six tips to help you write with accuracy and confidence. One of the simplest and most helpful ways to catch grammar errors is to read your writing aloud. When you do this, you can hear how your sentences sound, where you need to pause, and where you might have missed a word, a punctuation mark, or a verb tense. Reading aloud can also help you identify awkward phrasing, repetition, or ambiguity that you might not notice on the screen. You can read your writing aloud to yourself, or ask someone else to listen and give you feedback.

9. Sometimes, grammar errors are caused by a lack of understanding or confusion about the rules and conventions of the language. If you want to address these errors, you need to review the basics of grammar and refresh your knowledge. You can use online resources, such as Purdue OWL, Grammar Girl, or Khan Academy, to learn about topics such as parts of speech, sentence structure, verb tenses, subject-verb agreement, pronouns, modifiers, and more. You can

also practice your grammar skills with exercises, quizzes, and games. The final way to address grammar errors is to get feedback from others. Sometimes, you might not be able to spot your own errors or know how to correct them. That is why it is helpful to have someone else read your writing and give you constructive criticism. You can ask a friend, a colleague, a tutor, or a professional editor to review your writing and point out any grammar errors that they find. You can also ask them to explain why the errors are wrong and how to fix them. This way, you can learn from your mistakes and avoid making them again.

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